

Type of the Paper (Article)

Functional Properties Potential of Tempe Metabolites from Various Regions of West Java Analyzed Using Liquid Chromatography High-Resolution Mass Spectrometry (LC-HRMS)

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Abstract

Background/Objectives: Tempe, a traditional Indonesian fermented soybean food, is globally recognized for its nutritional and functional properties. This study aimed to comprehensively analyze tempe's metabolite compounds from five different regions in West Java using Liquid Chromatography High-Resolution Mass Spectrometry. The objective was to identify and characterize its metabolite profiles, including bioactive peptides and compounds with antioxidant capacity. **Methods:** Tempe samples were produced by local manufacturers using traditional methods. The research successfully identified diverse metabolite profiles across the samples. **Results:** LC-HRMS data revealed significant metabolite diversity, including *fatty acids*, *conjugated carbohydrates*, *Maillard products*, *saponins*, *surfactants*, *phosphates*, *alkaloids*, *terpenoids*, *amino sugar conjugates*, and *lipid-amines*. Measurements of antioxidant capacity, via ABTS and FRAP methods, showed variations: TB and TG exhibited the highest ABTS capacity (93.71 ppm and 93.61 ppm), while TC had the highest FRAP capacity (64.93 ppm). These variations indicate differences in bioactive antioxidant compounds. Macro-nutritional analysis confirmed tempe's consistent high nutritional value, with protein content ranging from 17.66% to 19.46%. **Conclusions:** Overall, these findings highlight that tempe from various West Java regions possesses unique metabolite profiles and diverse functional potential, particularly in terms of antioxidant capacity. The fermentation process enhances soybean's nutritional value and generates various bioactive compounds, such as isoflavones and bioactive peptides, contributing to its health benefits. This research provides a crucial basis for further studies and the development of optimized tempe products.

Keywords: Antioxydant capacity; Fermented soybean; Liquid Chromatography High-Resolution Mass Spectrometry; Metabolites; Tempe;

Academic Editor: Firstname Last-name

Received: date

Revised: date

Accepted: date

Published: date

Citation: To be added by editorial staff during production.

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1. Introduction

Tempe, a traditional Indonesian fermented soybean food, is globally recognized as a highly nutritious and functional food (1; 2; 3). Fermentation by *Rhizopus spp.* not only enhances the nutritional value of soybeans but also produces a variety of bioactive

compounds (2). This process releases enzymes that transform soybean proteins into bioactive peptides with various health benefits, including antioxidant, antihypertensive, antitumor, and antidiabetic activities (4; 5; 6;7; 8). Additionally, fermentation also increases the content and bioavailability of isoflavones like genistein, known as potent antioxidants and anticancer agents (9; 2).

One of tempe's primary benefits is its strong antioxidant capacity, which is significantly higher compared to raw soybeans (7; 8; 10; 11; 12; 13). Compounds such as isoflavones and bioactive peptides formed during fermentation work synergistically to scavenge free radicals and reduce oxidative stress (4; 12; 14). Research has also led to the identification of new antioxidant compounds from tempe, such as 3-hydroxyanthranilic acid, contributing to these antioxidant effects (15; 16).

Understanding tempe's metabolite profile, including bioactive peptides and antioxidant compounds, is crucial for optimizing its production and fully harnessing its health potential (2). For comprehensive metabolite identification and characterization, advanced analytical methods like Liquid Chromatography High-Resolution Mass Spectrometry are necessary (17). The combination of liquid chromatography with high-resolution mass spectrometry provides superior accuracy and sensitivity for separating, detecting, and identifying compounds in complex matrices (8; 18; 19; 20; 21; 22; 23). LC-HRMS has also proven highly effective in identifying antioxidant compounds (24; 25; 26; 27; 28; 29). Therefore, this study aims to comprehensively analyze tempe's metabolite compounds using LC-HRMS to identify and characterize its metabolite profile, including bioactive peptides and compounds with antioxidant capacity.

2. Materials and Methods

The materials used in the study were tempe from 5 different regions in West Java province produced by local manufacturers using traditional methods. The analytical materials used include: pH 7.0 phosphate buffer containing 1% SDS, FRAP reagent, ABTS reagent, Trolox, HPLC grade acetonitrile solvent, methanol, UHPLC C18 column. The equipment used includes: cool-box, freezer, freeze dryer, centrifuge, Liquid Chromatography High-Resolution Mass Spectrometry.

Sample Collection. Samples were collected from producers. Complete documentation on production methods, raw materials, and fermentation conditions will be gathered through interviews with producers. Sampling will be conducted using an aseptic protocol to minimize contamination. Samples will be stored in sterile containers at -20 °C during transportation to the laboratory, then at -80 °C for long-term storage prior to analysis. To ensure the samples represent commonly consumed products, sampling will be performed on products that are market-ready.

Sample Preparation. Extraction: Sample extraction was performed by the maceration method

Antioxidant Analysis. FRAP Assay. First, the working FRAP reagent is prepared. Then, a certain volume of sample (or Trolox/ascorbic acid standard) is mixed with the working FRAP reagent. The mixture is incubated at a specific temperature and for a certain time (e.g., 37°C for 30 minutes). Absorbance is then measured at a specific wavelength (e.g., 593 nm) using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Subsequently, a Trolox or ascorbic acid standard curve is constructed. Finally, the sample's FRAP capacity is calculated based on the standard curve and expressed as TEAC or Ascorbic Acid Equivalent. **ABTS (2,2'-Azinobis-(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) Assay.** Initially, the ABTS•+ radical cation solution is prepared by reacting ABTS with potassium persulfate and incubated in the dark. The ABTS•+ solution is then diluted to a specific absorbance at a particular wavelength. Next, a certain volume of sample (or Trolox/ascorbic

acid standard) is mixed with the ABTS•+ solution. The mixture is incubated for a specific time (e.g., 6 minutes). Absorbance is then measured at the same wavelength (734 nm) using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Subsequently, a Trolox or ascorbic acid standard curve is constructed. Finally, the sample's ABTS capacity is calculated based on the standard curve and expressed as TEAC.

Proximate Nutritional Analysis. To complement the antioxidant capacity analysis, the nutritional value of the samples will also be determined through a series of proximate analyses, including moisture content, ash content, protein content, fat content, carbohydrate content (by difference), and crude fiber content. **Determination of Moisture Content.** The sample is weighed, then dried in an oven at approximately 105°C until it reaches a constant weight. The difference in weight before and after drying is used to calculate the moisture content. **Determination of Ash Content.** The sample is weighed in a pre-weighed porcelain crucible, then incinerated in a muffle furnace at approximately 550°C-600°C until a white or constant ash is obtained. The remaining residue is weighed and used to calculate the ash content. **Determination of Protein Content.** The sample is digested with concentrated sulfuric acid and a catalyst to convert nitrogen into ammonium sulfate. Ammonium sulfate is converted into ammonia gas (NH₃) by adding strong NaOH, then distilled and captured in a boric acid solution. The captured ammonia is titrated with a standard acid to determine the amount of nitrogen. Protein content is calculated by multiplying the nitrogen content by the protein conversion factor. **Determination of Fat Content.** The dried sample is extracted with an organic solvent (hexane) using a Soxhlet apparatus. After the extraction is complete, the solvent is evaporated, and the remaining fat residue is weighed. **Determination of Crude Fiber Content.** The sample is refluxed with dilute sulfuric acid solution, then refluxed with dilute NaOH solution. The remaining residue is filtered, washed, dried, and incinerated. The difference in weight before and after incineration is the crude fiber content.

3. Results

This study identified various types of metabolite compounds and analyzed the antioxidant capacity and nutritional composition of tempe from several regions in West Java. The raw data for this interpretation is from your provided source (Table 1).

3.1. Tempe Metabolite Content

LC-HRMS data illustrates the diversity of metabolites in tempe from various regions (Table 1). **TG:** Rich in *fatty acids, conjugated carbohydrates, Maillard products, saponins, surfactants, phosphates, alkaloids, terpenoids, amino sugar conjugates, and lipid-amines*. **TT:** Contains *inorganics, amino-sugars, saponins, lipids, lipid amides, alkaloids, terpenoids, steroids, phospholipids, and flavonoids/isoflavones*. The presence of flavonoids/isoflavones is highly relevant for functional properties, including antioxidant and estrogen-like activities (30;31). **TB:** *Peptides, saponins, lipid amides, surfactants, inorganic phosphates, phosphates, phospholipids, amino acids, and nucleotides* were detected. Peptides and amino acids are protein degradation products that can possess bioactivity (6). **TC:** Contains *peptides, protein metabolites, saponins, lipids, lipid amines, lipid amides, lipid phosphates, sulfur AAs, terpenoids, and phospholipids*. **TS:** Identified *Maillard products, saponins, lipid-derived amides/surfactants, lipids, phospholipids, phosphates, synthetic heterocycles, heteroaromatics, sphingolipids, alkaloids, organosulfurs, amino acid derivatives, and terpenoids*. Generally, *saponins, lipids, alkaloids, and terpenoids* are consistent metabolites found across various tempe types, indicating a fundamental contribution from the soybean fermentation process (32).

3.2. Tempe Antioxidant Capacity

Measurements of antioxidant capacity using ABTS and FRAP methods show variation among samples (Table 2.). According to ABTS Radical Cation, TG have 93.61 ppm, TT 88.51 ppm, TB 93.71 ppm, TC 84.78 ppm (extract), and TS have 67.48 ppm. TB and TG exhibited the highest ABTS antioxidant capacity, while Subang Tempe showed the lowest. According to FRAP, TG have 57.39 ppm, TT 55.62 ppm, TB 58.71 ppm, TC 64.93 ppm, and TS have 41.46 ppm. TC recorded the highest FRAP antioxidant capacity, followed by TB, with TS having the lowest. These variations suggest differences in the content of bioactive antioxidant compounds among the tempe samples, often influenced by the fermentation process (8; 33).

3.3. Tempe Nutritional Content

Macro-nutritional content analysis revealed varying compositions (Table 1.). Protein ranged from 17.66% to 19.46%. TG had the highest protein content. Fat ranged from 1.82% to 4.73%. TC showed the highest fat content. Carbohydrate ranged from 9.34% to 10.63%. GT also had the highest carbohydrate content. Crude fiber ranged from 2.68% to 3.74%. TT contained the highest crude fiber. Moisture content varied between 66.01% and 67.92%. Ash content relatively stable, approximately 0.56% to 0.68%. Despite these variations, all tempe samples demonstrated a commendable nutritional profile, especially as a source of high-quality protein and fiber (34;35).

3.2. Figures, Tables and Schemes

Table 1. Nutritional content and crude fiber of tempeh and oncom from various regions in West Java

No.	Sample	Moisture (%)	Ash (%)	Lipid (%)	Protein (%)	Carbohydrate (%)	Crude fiber (%)
1	TG	66.60±0.25	0.56±0.16	2.77±0.01	19.46±0.09	10.63±0.18	2.68±0.01
2	TT	67.04±0.08	0.68±0.02	4.45±0.01	18.43±0.04	9.42±0.07	3.74±0.33
3	TB	67.92±0.84	0.64±0.06	2.69±0.11	19.33±0.11	9.44±1.11	3.36±0.46
4	TC	66.01±0.67	0.65±0.00	4.73±0.33	19.28±0.42	9.34±0.57	3.55±0.47
5	TS	69.53±0.13	0.57±0.00	1.82±0.06	17.66±0.43	10.43±0.36	3.54±0.10

Table 2. Antioxidant capacity of tempeh and oncom from various regions in West Java using the ABTS radical cation and FRAP methods

No.	Sample	ABTS radical cation				FRAP	
		Capacity against Trolox (ppm)	Capacity against Trolox (ppm) mg/g extract	Capacity against Trolox (ppm) mg/g sample	Capacity against Trolox (ppm)	Capacity against Trolox (ppm) mg/g extract	Capacity against Trolox (ppm) mg/g sample
1	TG	93.61	15.9740	1.4609	57.39	9.7930	0.8956
2	TT	88.51	15.0017	1.2531	55.62	9.4271	0.7875
3	TB	93.71	11.8916	1.2298	58.71	7.4501	0.7705

4	TC	84.78	12.1294	1.1987	64.93	9.2884	0.9179
5	TS	67.48	9.8800	0.7809	41.46	6.0701	0.4798

Table 3. Types of metabolite compounds found in tempeh and oncom from various regions in West Java

No.	Sample	Type of metabolite compound
1	TG	Fatty acid Conjugated carbohydrate Maillard product Saponin Surfactant Phosphate Alkaloid Terpenoid Amino sugar conjugate Lipid-amine
2	TT	Anorganic Amino-sugar Saponin Lipid Lipid amide Alkaloid Terpenoid Steroid Phospholipid Flavonoid / isoflavone
3	TB	Peptida Saponin Lipid amide Surfaktan Lipid amide Phosphate inorganic Phosphate Phospholipid Amino acid Nukleotida
4	TC	Peptida Metabolite protein Saponin Lipid Lipid amine Lipid amide Lipid Phosphate

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		AA sulfur
		Terpenoid
		Phospholipid
5	TS	Maillard product
		Saponin
		Lipid-derived amide/surfactant
		Lipid
		Phospholipid
		Phosphate
		Synthetic heterocycle
		Heteroaromatic
		Sphingolipid
		Alkaloid
		Organosulfur
		Amino acid derivative
		Terpenoid
		Peptidic glycoside
		Amino acid
		Purine
		Nucleotide
		Flavonoid/isoflavone
		Halogenated organic acid
		Flavonoid / polyphenol
		Lipid glycoside
		Nucleobase

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4. Discussion

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This study successfully identified and compared the metabolite profiles and functional properties of tempe sourced from five regions in West Java (Table 3). The application of the LC-HRMS approach facilitated the detection of various bioactive compounds that contribute to tempe's health potential (6).

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The observed diversity of metabolites, including *fatty acids*, *saponins*, *alkaloids*, *terpenoids*, *peptides*, *amino acids*, and notably *flavonoids/isoflavones* (particularly in TT), suggests that tempe is not merely an excellent plant-based protein source but is also rich in bioactive compounds offering potential health benefits (32; 34). *Flavonoids* and *isoflavones* are recognized as potent antioxidants and possess estrogen-like activities, which can play a role in the prevention of chronic diseases (30; 36; 37). *Saponins* are known for their hypocholesterolemic properties by inhibiting cholesterol absorption (38; 39), while *peptides* and *amino acids*, derived from protein degradation during fermentation, may exhibit antihypertensive or immunomodulatory activities (6; 8).

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Significant variations in antioxidant capacity among the tempe samples indicate that environmental conditions, soybean cultivars, or distinct fermentation practices in each region can influence the formation of antioxidant compounds (10; 33). For instance, TB and TG displayed high ABTS activity, whereas TC excelled in FRAP activity. These

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differences might be linked to the specific concentrations of antioxidant metabolites such as flavonoids, terpenoids, or Maillard products accumulated during fermentation (8). TS generally exhibited lower antioxidant capacity compared to other samples, suggesting potential factors limiting antioxidant compound formation in that region. The fermentation process itself is known to increase the antioxidant activity of soybeans (10; 36).

Furthermore, the analysis of macro-nutritional content affirms that tempe from various regions in West Java consistently serves as a highly nutritious food (34). Its high protein content underscores its role as a vital dietary protein source, while adequate crude fiber contributes to digestive health (35; 40). Minor differences in fat, protein, and carbohydrate levels may stem from variations in soybean raw materials or discrepancies in processing and fermentation methods. Tempe fermentation also improves the bioavailability of minerals, proteins, fiber, vitamins, and isoflavones (41).

Overall, these data highlight that tempe from various regions of West Java possesses unique metabolite profiles and diverse functional potential, especially concerning antioxidant capacity. The findings of this research provide a crucial foundation for further studies on the isolation and characterization of specific bioactive compounds from local tempe, as well as for developing tempe products with optimized health benefits (34).

4.1. Protein Content and Its Role in Metabolite Profile and Antioxidant Capacity

While tempe is naturally rich in protein (as seen in TG, TT, TB, and TC tempe with protein content ranging from 17.66% to 19.46% (Table 2), the fermentation process by *Rhizopus* sp. plays a crucial role in converting these macromolecular proteins into more bioactive compounds. During fermentation, soybean proteins undergo degradation or hydrolysis into smaller peptides and free amino acids (8). This process increases the soluble protein content and small-sized peptides. For example, TB and TC have *peptides* and *protein metabolites* in their metabolite profiles (Table 3). These degraded peptides, known as bioactive peptides, exhibit various functional activities, including antioxidant properties (6). Research indicates that fermented tempe has higher levels of bioactive peptides compared to unfermented soybeans, and these peptides can withstand the digestive process, maintaining their antioxidant activity (42).

4.2. Metabolite Profile and Its Contribution to Antioxidant Capacity

The metabolite profile of tempe is highly diverse and includes a variety of bioactive compounds that collectively contribute to its antioxidant capacity. The fermentation process not only breaks down proteins but also modifies other existing compounds and even generates new metabolites. Fermentation increases the release and bioavailability of phenolic compounds, flavonoids, and proanthocyanidins from soybeans (8). These compounds are potent antioxidants (12; 14). For instance, TT was identified to contain *flavonoids/isoflavones* (Table 3.), which are known to possess significant antioxidant potential (4). The antioxidant capacity of tempe does not stem from a single type of compound but rather from the synergy of various metabolites. In addition to peptides and phenolic compounds, other metabolites such as *saponins*, *alkaloids*, and *terpenoids* (found in almost all tempe samples from West Java (Table 3.) can also contribute to antioxidant activity and other health benefits (32; 39). TG and TS contain *Maillard products* (Table 3.). Maillard reaction products can also exhibit antioxidant properties.

4.3. Direct Link: Fermentation as the Key

Fermentation is the fundamental process that integrates these three aspects: Protein modification: This process directly alters protein structures, generating bioactive peptides that enhance antioxidant capacity. Metabolite profile changes: Fermentation modifies the soybean matrix, releasing bound phenolic compounds and increasing the levels of more absorbable aglycone isoflavones, as well as producing other antioxidant metabolites (8; 41). Increased antioxidant capacity: Overall, the changes in protein and metabolite profiles during fermentation lead to a significant increase in tempe's antioxidant capacity compared to unfermented soybeans (8).

In summary, the high protein content in tempe (Table 1.) serves as a primary substrate for *Rhizopus* fungi to produce bioactive peptides during fermentation. These peptides, along with phenolic compounds, isoflavones, and other metabolites, synergistically enhance tempe's antioxidant capacity. The observed differences in antioxidant capacity among tempe samples from various regions in West Java likely reflect variations in specific metabolite profiles influenced by soybean cultivars, fermentation conditions, and the type of starter used in each area.

5. Conclusions

Tempe from various West Java regions possesses unique metabolite profiles and diverse functional potential, particularly in terms of antioxidant capacity. The fermentation process enhances soybean's nutritional value and generates various bioactive compounds, such as isoflavones and bioactive peptides, contributing to its health benefits.

6. Patents

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Supplementary Materials: -

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, N.E.P, R.I., and P.Y.F.; methodology, N.T.; software, N.E.P and R.I.; validation, R.I., P.Y.F and N.T.; formal analysis, N.T.; investigation, N.T.; resources, N.E.P, R.I., and P.Y.F.; data curation, R.I., P.Y.F and N.T.; writing—original draft preparation, N.E.P, and R.I.; writing—review and editing, N.T and P.Y.F.; visualization, R.I.; supervision, R.I and N.T.; project administration, N.E.P; funding acquisition, N.E.P. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.”

Funding: This research was funded by Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Technology of the Republic of Indonesia. Regular fundamental research Batch II. Master Grant Number 195/C3/DT.05.00/PL-BATCH II/2025 and derivative Grant Number 3167/PL25/AL.04/2025.

Institutional Review Board Statement: -

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable

Data Availability Statement: We encourage all authors of articles published in MDPI journals to share their research data. In this section, please provide details regarding where data supporting reported results can be found, including links to publicly archived datasets analyzed or generated during the study. Where no new data were created, or where data is unavailable due to privacy or ethical restrictions, a statement is still required. Suggested Data Availability Statements are available in section “MDPI Research Data Policies” at <https://www.mdpi.com/ethics>.

Acknowledgments: In this section, you can acknowledge any support given which is not covered by the author contribution or funding sections. This may include administrative and technical support, or donations in kind (e.g., materials used for experiments). Where GenAI has been used for purposes such as generating text, data, or graphics, or for study design, data collection, analysis, or interpretation of data, please add “During the preparation of this manuscript/study, the author(s)

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Conflicts of Interest: The author sincerely acknowledges the financial support provided by the Directorate General of Research and Development, Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Technology of the Republic of Indonesia through the 2025 research grant program. This support was instrumental in conducting and completing the research presented in this article.

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

MDPI	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute
DOAJ	Directory of open access journals
TLA	Three letter acronym
LD	Linear dichroism

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